

Research article**ASSESSMENT OF SAWMILL SOLID WASTE IMPACT ON PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SOIL AROUND SAWMILL DUMPING SITES IN AKURE METROPOLIS, SOUTHWEST, NIGERIA****¹Ibitoye*, A. A., ²Amoo, I. A., and ³Tomori, W. B.**

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Abstract

Sawdust is one of the by-products of sawmills operations generated in huge heaps in the timber industry which are not properly disposed. The massive wastes accumulated are underutilized which has become a serious environmental problem. When left on the ground for a long period of time will affect the composition of soil on which they were deposited. This research work is to assess sawmill solid wastes impact on the physicochemical properties of soil around sawmill dump sites in Akure metropolis, Southwest, Nigeria. Composite soil samples were collected randomly at 0-30 cm depth and at intervals of 0, 10, 25 and 50 meters from three different sawmills and were prepared for analysis. The prepared samples were analyzed for their physicochemical properties using standard methods. The range of soil physicochemical properties obtained are: moisture content, (15.33 to 45.27 %); water holding capacity, (32.16 to 51.32 %); porosity, (36.32 - 48.21 %); soil texture: sand (41 to 67 %); silt (13 to 24 %), clay, (17 to 39 %); pH, (6.03 to 7.95); organic matter, (1.82 to 44.41 %); available phosphorus, (1.47 to 48.77 mg/kg); total nitrogen, (0.17 to 1.17 %); potassium, (78 to 663 mg/kg); sodium, (36.80 to 375 mg/kg); calcium, (1200 to 4800 mg/kg); magnesium, (350 to 1320) mg/kg; zinc, (0.20 to 3.01 mg/kg); iron, (1.19 to 129.0 mg/kg); Heavy metals were generally low where detected. The study revealed that sawmill wastes impacted significantly on soil physical properties and nutrient status. Soils within 0.00 – 25.00 meters from refuse dump site can be used as top soil for backyard farming or nursery garden.

Introduction

The term sawmill could refer to a location where lumbers are milled. Bodig and Jayne, (1993) defined sawmill as the entire system that turns logs into lumber. Wood processing industry being relatively available in many locations in Nigeria contributed to huge heap of wood wastes within sawmills. Large number of wood wastes are generated as a result of increased demand of wood and wood products, which become environmentally hazardous. This wood wastes have been neglected in Nigeria because many consider them useless and of no importance. In almost all sawmill industries within Akure metropolis, wood wastes are dumped around its premises causing environmental pollution and fire hazards. Many states in Nigeria have difficulties in handling these wastes thus making the environment very unhealthy and is affecting the quality of life in those areas. This also poses danger to other unseen aspects of the environment such as water bodies, air and soils (Nnamdi, 2014).

It is important to note that soil is a principal recipient of solid waste. Soils are highly variable in nature, this variation includes their structure, layering, colour, range of particle sizes, chemistry, nutrients, acidity, temperature, water content, thickness, organic content, and its associated biota (Kebede *et al.*, 2018). These properties vary because of differences in the parent material, climate, topography, organic content, and the amount of time it has to develop (Kebede *et al.*, 2018). Changes in one or more of these factors may drastically alter the soil physical, chemical and biological properties (Piccolo and Mbagwu, 1997; Kebede *et al.*, 2018). The huge sawmill wastes can improve or degrade the physical and chemical properties of soil (Fatihu *et al.*, 2022). Sawmill wastes disposal is a major environmental problem in many urban centers owing to the methods of disposal and management, (Anikwe and Nwobodo, 2002; Obike-Martins *et al.*, 2021; Oluwatoyin, *et al.*, 2021). Continuous dumping of sawmill wastes on soil may bring about a great change to particle size distribution (soil texture) and increase heavy metal levels (Smith *et al.*, 1993). Understanding specific characteristics of each soil is necessary when

dealing with wastes impact on soil such as physical and chemical qualities assist in resource management (Brady and Weil, 2002; Mir *et al.*, 2022). Lack of effective sawmill waste management in growing populated sawmill industry have substantial negative impact on the environment including soil (Oluwatoyi, *et al.*, 2021). Organic waste and mulches are said to help improve soil aeration, increase nutrient capacities, structural development, and drainage reduce leaching which will go a long way in aiding recovery of the degraded nutrients (Kebede *et al.*, 2018). It is observed that soil differs in their response to organic waste amendments and that it is important to investigate more closely the influence of this organic and inorganic accumulation on a range of soil physical and chemical properties (Akintola *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, the objective of this work is to assess the physical and chemical properties of soil around sawmill industry as influenced by decayed organic matters in Akure metropolis.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study area covers Akure South and Ifedore Local Government Areas in Ondo State, South Western Nigeria. Location A (Armanda international limited, Ilesa/Benin road, Akure) lies on latitude 7.28585°N and longitude 5.16803°E; location B (kinrele mumuni sawmill Ilara Mokin) lies on latitude 7.34186°N and longitude 5.10235°E; and location C (Ise Oluwa sawmill Ondo road, Akure) lies on latitude 7.25475°N longitude 5.10235°E; Spatial positioning of different sawmill locations were collected through the use of a hand held Global Positioning System (GPS) Garmin model etrex 10 and the software used to generate the study area map was ArcGIS 10.5 by ESRI presented in Figure 1.

The climatic condition of Akure metropolis follows the pattern of south western Nigeria where the climate is influenced mainly by the rain-bearing southwest monsoon winds from the ocean and the dry northwest winds from the Sahara Desert. Akure experiences a warm humid tropical climate, with two distinct seasons, the rainy and dry seasons. The rainy season lasts for about seven months, April to October (Balogun *et al.*, 2011).

Samples for this study were collected from three (3) locations within the study area (Figure 1). Composite samples of soil were collected randomly using soil auger at (0-30 cm) depth at intervals of 0, 10 and 25 m while the control was taken at 50 m. The soil samples were air dried, disaggregated with the aid of mortar and pestle, passed through 2 mm sieve and stored in labeled polyethylene nylon bags.

Fig.1: Map of sampling locations

The soil moisture content, was determined according to methods describe by AOAC (2005). Bulk density and particle size analysis were determined according to methods describe by Carter, (1992). The pH of soil suspension in ratio 1:2 soil and water using pH meter model PHS-3C and particle size was determine using the hydrometer method described by FAO Bulletin no 19, (2008); Ubuoh, *et al.* (2012). Organic matter was determined using method described by Inengite *et al.* (2015). The total nitrogen was determined using micro-kjeldahl method described by Carter and Gregorich, (2006). The available phosphorus was extracted with Bray-1 reagents solution and concentration determined by spectrophotometry using molybdenum blue method (Carter and Gregorich, 2006). The exchangeable cations were extracted by leaching 10 g of soil with 100 ml of one molar neutral ammonium acetate solution (pH 7). The sodium and potassium in the leachate were determined with flame photometer Jenway model PFP7 while the calcium and magnesium were determined with atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) Buck scientific model 210 at 422.7 and 285.2nm wavelength respectively. Soil samples were digested for heavy metals using mixture of concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl) in a ratio of 1:3, the digests were analyzed using (AAS (Adamu, 2014; Ogbonna *et al.*, 2018). The data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the mean separated by Duncan's multiple range using SPSS package.

Results and Discussion

The results of analysis on physical properties of soil within sawmill environment are presented in Figures 2 and 3. Figure 2 shows percentage soil moisture content, water holding capacity and porosity). High values of WHC, moisture content and porosity show the

influence of organic matter from sawmill wastes on soil physical properties. The error bar shows standard deviation of different samples. The mean moisture content (%) of soil ranged between 15.33 and 45.27 with highest percentage at a depth of 0 m and lowest percentage at control (50 m). The results showed decrease in moisture content with increase in distance from 0 m to 50 m. Water holding capacity (WHC) % ranged between 32.16 and 51.32 with highest percentage at distance 0 m and lowest percentage at control (50 m). The results also showed decrease in WHC with increase in distance from 0 m to 50 m and porosity % ranged between (36.32 and 48.21) with highest percentage at distance 0 m and lowest percentage at control (50 m). The results show decrease in porosity with increase in distance from 0 m to 50 m. The high values of moisture content, WHC and porosity obtained from these results may be associated with organic matter distribution around sawmill dumpsites. The result is similar to the study of Akintola, et al. (2022) with range of 18.05 and 38.11 % organic matter. Significant differences were also noticed in the mean values of the moisture content, water holding capacity and the porosity of the soils from the three locations at $P < 0.05$. The significant differences observed from moisture content, water holding capacity and porosity values from the dumpsite soils when compared to the control is similar to the study conducted by Njoku (2015) and Agbeshie et al. (2020). Thus, the determined physical conditions from dumpsite soils are greatly affected when compared to soils from the control due to the quality and quantity of organic matters present (Indorial et al., 2017

WHC = water holding capacity

Fig. 2 Soil moisture content, WHC and porosity around sawmill environment

The results of particle size analysis (also known as textural analysis) are shown in Figure 3. The class of

soil is sandy clay loam for soil between 0.00 and 10 m from dumpsite and sandy loam for soil between 25 and 50 m from dumpsite. The mean range of soil textural classes for distances 0, 10, 25 and 50.00 m in the three locations are: sand (41 to 67 %); silt, (13 to 24%); and clay (17 to 39%) respectively. Sand has the lowest percentage at 0 m and highest at control (50 m). Silt and clay have highest value at 0 m and lowest at control (50 m). The percentage (%) sand across the three sampling areas increases with increased in distance from 0 m through 50 m, while silt and clay decrease with increased distance from 0 m through 50 m. However, significant differences were observed in their mean values at $P < 0.05$ (Figure 1). High level of clay within sawmill wastes could be associated with organic matter contents. Akintola, et al. (2022); Indorial et al. (2017) stated that the nature and quality of soil structure are strongly affected by the quantity and quality of organic matter in the soil. Thus, soils from the dumpsite will have more stable structure, high moisture content, water retention and porosity. (Gurber et al., 2014; Hatten and Lilles, 2019).

The frequent addition of easily decomposable organic residues to soil causes the synthesis of complex organic compounds that bind soil particles into structural units called aggregates (Aluko and Oyeleke 2005). These aggregates help to maintain a loose open, granular condition. Water is then better able to enter and percolate downward through the soil with pollutants, (Aluko and Oyeleke 2005). The environmental behavior of physicochemical parameters, including the macro and micro elements, and others, is significantly influenced by soil particle size (Agboola and Fagbenro, 1985; Aluko and Oyeleke, 2005). In general, clay soils are better at delivering nutrients and holding more water. This work is similar to the study of Akintola et al. (2022).

Fig. 3: The Mean Results of Physical Properties of Soil (Particle size Analysis)

The results of soil chemical parameters are shown in Table 1. The results show analysis of soil from four different distances: 0.00, 10.00, 25.00, and 50.00 m. The pH of the studied soils ranged from 6.03 (slightly acidic) to 7.95 (moderately alkaline) in nature, this agreed with findings on dumpsites by Mouhoun-Chouaki *et al.* (2019); Agbeshie *et al.* (2020). Soils from 0 m dumpsite have the highest pH while control (50 m) soils have the lowest value. No significant difference was noticed among the three locations. The higher pH values recorded in the dumpsite soils could be attributed to high exchangeable bases Na, K, Ca and Mg (Agbeshie *et al.*, 2020). One of the most significant chemical characteristics is the pH of soil which influences other parameters. It has an impact on the quality of the soil's chemical properties and many microorganism activities (Borkar, 2015; Georgiou *et al.*, 2022). The results of soil pH 0-25 m are slightly higher than 6-7 FAO standards, (FAO publication on soil bulletins No 63).

Soil samples from the three studied locations have the organic matter content ranged from 1.82 to 44.41%. Soils from 0 m dumpsite have the highest organic value, while control (50 m) soils have the lowest value. There is no significant difference in the organic matter (OM) concentration (%) for distances 0 m and 10 m in samples from locations A and C including the 0 m distance of sampling location B; similar to 25 and 50 m distances for sampling location C and 10 m of sampling location B. In the same vein, organic carbon (OC) concentrations follow the same arrangements with organic matter. The results of (OM) showed no significant difference for distances 0 and 10 m for locations A. There was significant difference between 10 m and 25 m but no significant difference between 25 m and 50 m for location B but there was significant difference for all the distances in location C. The results show similarity in nutrient distribution for the three locations. Organic carbon and organic matter decreased with increase distances from 0 and 50 meters. Soil organic matter strongly affects nutrient storage and its availability in soils (Hoffland *et al.*, 2020; Gerke, 2022).. Organic matter increases soil structural stability and resistance to rainfall impact (Roose and Barthes 2001; Ubuoh, et al., 2012). These high values are indication of pollution. The result of percentage nitrogen content in the soil samples ranged from 0.17 and 1.17 %. Soils from 0 m dumpsite have the highest nitrogen value, while control (50 m) soils have the lowest value. No significant difference was noticed among soils within locations A 0 to 50 m, location B and C 0 to 10 m. Locations B distances 25 to 50 m showed no significant difference. Locations C distance 25 and 50 m showed no significant difference.

Figure 4. Mean Results of pH, OC, OM and N of Soil within Sawmill Environment

The concentrations of P, K, Na, Ca, and Mg of soil across sampling distances and locations within the sawmill area are presented in Table 1. Four different distances were considered in the study: 0.00, 10.00, 25.00, and 50.00 m for the three different sampling areas. The concentration values of phosphorus (P) ranged between (1.47 and 48.77) mg/kg. There was significant difference between organic rich areas from 0 to 25 m and the control distance 50 m. The highest values were recorded at distance of 0 m for locations (A, B and C) and lowest values at control points (50 m). But generally, nutrients distribution decrease with increase in distance from waste dumpsites. The nutrient content at 50 m from dumpsite is generally lower than other organic rich distances of 0 to 25 m from dumpsite. The results of available phosphorus are lower than (47 mg/kg) reported by Okonkwo *et al.* (2013).

The potassium (K) concentration values across the three sampling locations A, B, and C ranged between (78 and 663) mg/kg with lowest concentration recorded at location A distance 0 m. This study showed higher potassium content than what was reported (13.84mg/kg) in the study of Okonkwo *et al.*, (2013). These high values may be as a result of geographical location, wood type and wood treatment. Lack of K or inadequate K supply will impede plant growth and lower yield. Additionally, potassium aids in controlling the stomata's opening and shutting, which controls the exchange of water vapor, oxygen, and carbon dioxide (Nguemezi *et al.*, 2020; Pahalvi, *et al.*, 2021).

The concentration of Na ranged between (36.80 and 375) mg/kg. Sodium (Na) showed no significant difference for distances 0 to 25 m in sampling locations A; 0 to 50 m in location B and 0 to 25 m for location C. No significant difference with distances 25.00 and 50.00 m of sampling location A and 50.00 m of

sampling location C. The results of sodium in this study are higher than what was reported (18) mg/kg by Azuka and Chikamso, (2023). There are significant differences between the sawmill dumpsites and the control. Sodium concentrations decrease with increased distances from dumpsite for the three locations.

Concentration of calcium (Ca) ranged between (1200 and 4800) mg/kg. There was no significant difference in the concentration values obtained for distances 0, 10 and 25 m for sampling locations A, B and C but significantly different from the control (50 m). The values are generally higher at 0 m than others and lowest values at control (50 m). Calcium had the highest mean concentrations among the exchangeable bases in the studied area with highest concentration values at distance 0 m and lowest at control. The concentration values of distances (0 and 10) m in location A and B were found to be higher than (2600) mg/kg reported by Azuka and Chikamso (2023).

The values obtained for magnesium (Mg) ranged between (350 and 1320) mg/kg. These results are lower than 1360 mg/kg reported by Azuka and Chikamso, (2023). The values obtained for magnesium has the highest value at distance 0 m and lowest at control (50) m. Mg showed no significant difference in

distances (0, 10, and 25.00) m of sampling location A, but significantly different to control. Sampling location B, (0, 10 and 25) m are significantly different to the control. Sampling location C showed no significant difference between distance 25 m and control. Magnesium is critical in the activation of particular enzyme systems (Cole et al., 2016; Tian et al., 2021). Organic acids are created during plant cell metabolism and can be neutralized with the assistance of calcium, magnesium, and potassium. Additionally, calcium aids in the root's ability to absorb other nutrients and the movement of those elements throughout the plant (Pennand and Camberato, 2019; Nguemezi et al., 2020; Meyer, et al., 2020; Tianet, et al., 2021).

The high organic matter and exchangeable bases recorded in distances 0.00, 10.00 and 25 meters also affirmed the highest mean pH value in all the three locations, thus indicating the influence of Na, K, Ca and Mg on soil pH (Agbeshie et al., 2020). Generally, concentrations of K, Na and Ca are higher than FAO standards of 59-160, 60-120 and 1150-3500 mg/kg respectively. The relative high exchangeable bases in the studied sites is an indication of increase in nutrient availability and soil microbial activities (Okonkwo et al., 2013; Herrero et al., 2021), thus the soil will be good as top soil for nursery farm and backyard farming.

Table 2: Results of P, K, Na, Ca, and Mg of Soil per Location and Sample Distance Within the Sawmill Area

Location	Distance (m)	P (mg/kg)	K (mg/kg)	Na (mg/kg)	Ca (mg/kg)	Mg (mg/kg)
A	0	48.77±0.39 ^a	663.00±10.25 ^a	340.00±15.05 ^a	4800±67.55 ^a	1320±23.46 ^a
	10	16.41±1.05 ^b	546.00±10.51 ^a	167.00±17.18 ^a	2800±56.84 ^a	720±37.36 ^a
	25	12.21±0.46 ^b	265.00±10.01 ^{ab}	73.00±19.27 ^b	2520±50.72 ^a	576±47.83 ^a
	50	6.41±0.55 ^c	78.00±10.75 ^c	36.80±15.05 ^b	1200±17.55 ^b	360±33.46 ^{ab}
B	0	40.56±0.85 ^a	624.00±10.25 ^a	188.00±13.78 ^a	2240±62.60 ^a	768±28.24 ^a
	10	11.82±0.39 ^b	390.00±11.58 ^b	169.00±16.58 ^a	1640±53.12 ^a	408±36.47 ^b
	25	15.37±1.00 ^b	310.00±11.16 ^b	126.00±17.18 ^a	1540±36.84 ^a	456±27.36 ^b
	50	5.21±1.40 ^c	140.00±15.52 ^c	94.00±13.78 ^b	1280±62.60 ^b	360±18.24 ^{ab}
C	0	45.57±1.44 ^a	636.00±15.25 ^a	375.00±14.04 ^a	3200±51.72 ^a	960±48.30 ^a
	10	14.93±0.89 ^b	339.00±17.51 ^b	285.00±19.27 ^a	2960±50.72 ^a	716±56.83 ^a
	25	10.50±1.16 ^b	207.00±10.01 ^b	223.00±16.58 ^a	2400±43.12 ^a	528±47.17 ^b
	50	1.47±0.52 ^c	140.00±12.75 ^c	126.00±14.04 ^b	1360±41.72 ^b	380±38.30 ^{ab}

Heavy metals in soil samples for the three sampling locations A, B, and C across the four sampling distances (0, 10, 25, and 50) m are shown in Table 4. From the result, the concentration of cadmium (Cd)

ranged from (not detected to 0.21) mg/kg and decreases with increase in distance from sawmill refuse dump site. There is a growing environmental concern about Cd being one of the most eco-toxic

metals, exhibiting highly adverse effects on soil health, biological activity, plant metabolism, and the health of humans and animals (Kabata-Pendias, 2001). Concentration of iron ranged from 1.19 to 123 mg/kg. There was no significant difference in the concentrations of iron (Fe) for locations A distance 0.00 m, location B distances 0.00 and 10.00 m and location C distances 0.00, 10.00, and 25.00 m while that of sampling locations A distances 10.00 and 25.00 m, location B distance 25.00 m), and location C distance 50.00 m showed no significant difference. The concentration of Fe for sampling locations A and B for 50.00 m distances also showed no significant difference. Zinc (Zn) concentration (mg/kg) ranged from 0.02 and 3.10. Zn was detected from all the sampling locations across the various distances. There was no significant difference in the concentration values of Zn from sampling location A distances 0.00 and 10.00 m; location B distances 0, 10, 25, 50 m and location C distances (0 and 10) m. Chromium (Cr) and nickel (Ni) were not detected from all the sampling locations across the various distances sampled. The

concentration of copper (Cu) ranged from 0.02 to 0.43 mg/kg. There were no significant differences for sampling locations A distances 0.00 and 10.00 m, location B distances 0.00, 25.00, and 50.00 m and location C distances 0.00, 10.00, and 25.00 m. While that of sampling location A distance 25.00 m and location C distance 50.00 m show no significant difference. Copper was not detected only in sampling location A distance 50.00 m. The concentration of lead (Pb) shows no significant difference for sampling locations A distance 0.00 m, location B distances 0.00 and 10.00 m and location C 0.00 m. In similar way, there is no significant difference in the Pb concentration for sampling location C distances 10.00 and 25.00 m distances while Pb was not detected in the others sampling locations C (10.00, 25.00, and 50.00 m), B (25.00 and 50.00 m), and C (50.00 m). Accumulation of heavy metals in the soil and plants negatively affects their physiological processes like photosynthesis, gas exchange, and nutrient uptake, which reduces plant development and causes the buildup of dry matter. (Mouhoun-Chouaki et al., 2019)

Table 3: heavy metals of Soil per Location and Sample Distance within Sawmill Area

Location	Distance (m)	Cd (mg/kg)	Cr (mg/kg)	Fe (mg/kg)	Zn (mg/kg)	Ni (mg/kg)	Cu (mg/kg)	Pb (mg/kg)
A	0.00	0.13±0.01 ^a	ND	111±6.13 ^a	2.24±0.40 ^a	ND	0.32±0.02 ^a	0.05±0.01 ^a
	10.00	0.11±0.01 ^a	ND	67±1.66 ^b	2.10±0.01 ^a	ND	0.15±0.05 ^a	ND
	25.00	ND	ND	47±1.43 ^b	0.02±0.00 ^b	ND	0.04±0.00 ^b	ND
	50.00	ND	ND	5.03±9.34 ^c	0.12±0.00 ^b	ND	ND	ND
B	0.00	0.21±0.01 ^a	ND	123±0.04 ^a	1.17±0.00 ^a	ND	0.41±0.08 ^a	0.04±0.01 ^a
	10.00	0.14±0.01 ^a	ND	119±1.03 ^a	0.58±0.01 ^a	ND	0.04±0.01 ^b	0.02±0.01 ^a
	25.00	0.08±0.01 ^a	ND	75±1.59 ^b	0.45±0.01 ^a	ND	0.27±0.05 ^a	ND
	50.00	ND	ND	15±5.00 ^c	0.92±0.02 ^a	ND	0.18±0.03 ^a	ND
C	0.00	0.17±0.01 ^a	ND	82±0.18 ^a	3.10±0.50 ^a	0.01±0.00	0.43±0.03 ^a	0.29±0.04 ^a
	10.00	0.05±0.01 ^b	ND	65±1.26 ^a	2.15±0.40 ^a	ND	0.32±1.02 ^a	0.06±0.02 ^b
	25.00	ND	ND	24±2.71 ^a	1.09±0.03 ^b	ND	0.17±0.03 ^a	0.03±0.01 ^b
	50.00	ND	ND	1.19±0.07 ^b	0.49±0.04 ^b	ND	0.02±0.00 ^b	ND

Location A: Armanda international limited, Ilesa/Benin road, Akure
 Location B: Akinrele Mumuni sawmill Ilara Mokin
 Location C: Ise Oluwa sawmill Ondo Road, Akure

Conclusion

This study evaluated some physical and chemical properties of soil around sawmill areas in Akure metropolis. The study revealed that sawmill wastes impacted significantly on soil texture, moisture, pH content, organic matter, phosphorous and

exchangeable. Heavy metals concentrations were not detected in many samples and generally low where detected. The low results of heavy metals further suggests that the dump is free from industrial wastes. The high pH values and organic matter content in the dump site increased the soil nutrient contents such as exchangeable bases and micronutrient, thus

enhancing soil microbial activities, fertility and productivity status of the soil for maximum plant growth. In general, the soils under evaluation reflected some response to wood wastes when compared with control distance 50 meters and above. Soils within 0.00 – 25.00 meters from refuse dump site can be used as top soil for backyard farming or nursery garden. Reuse and recycling should be encouraged to reduce the massive sawmill wastes and pollution over time.

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